

THE POWER OF CONNECTIONS

Harvesting Lessons and Strengthening Coalitions for Amazonian Conservation

Executive Analysis

Reshaping institutions for next generation conservation leaders in the Amazon

This publication serves as the Executive Analysis of Workshop 2, part of the project “Power of Connections: Harvesting Lessons and Strengthening Coalitions for Amazonian Conservation.”

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Organizers

Collaborator

Partner

Initiatives that promote positive change for Amazon Conservation Leadership

1. Youth motivation through influence

Youth engagement is greatly influenced by others (family, mentors, peers).

• Examples:

- IBIF trainers as mentors in Bolivia
- Grandparents' land struggles as motivational drivers
- Family support enabling participation

2. Strategic youth activities

Well-organized, strategic activities gradually motivate youth.

• Examples:

- Tropenbos Colombia: Teacher training for intercultural curricula
- Bolivia's Indigenous Governance School: Youth leadership in territories
- Indigenous Journalism School: Technical skill development

3. Addressing key competencies

Key competencies are gradually being addressed through targeted programs.

• Examples:

- IBIF, APCOB, CNAMIB: Communication and leadership courses
- University curricula integrating conflict management skills
- Project design training for conservation initiatives

4. Higher education access innovation

Creative initiatives promote higher education access.

• Examples:

- Brazil: 10% minority quotas in public universities
- Brazil: University of Pará & IPÊ with Amazon-focused hybrid programs
- PUCE Ecuador: Graduate programs in Amazonian issues

5. Breaking educational conventions

Innovative approaches break with conventional education

• Examples:

- Forests School Network in Ecuador: "Learning through play, forest as classroom"
- PBACC Bolivia: Dinosaur costume for climate education
- Art-based environmental education methods

6. Gender role evolution

Changing gender roles and institutional initiatives support women's leadership

• Examples:

- Generational shift in traditional expectations
- IBIF Bolivia: Gender perspective on youth capacity building
- Family support enabling women's participation

7. Support systems for equality

Family and institutional support reduce gender gaps in education access

• Examples:

- CNAMIB in Bolivia: Women empowerment courses
- IKIAM University in Ecuador: Scholarships for adolescent mothers
- IBIF in Bolivia: Childcare services and flexible scheduling

8. Refocused education attributes

Refocused attributes of education for conservation leaders are essential

• Key Attributes:

- Transformative & inclusive
- Contextualized & intercultural
- Intergenerational & collaborative
- Values-based & practical

Introduction

Recognizing that the Amazon—one of the most diverse and vital ecosystems on the planet—is deeply interconnected with global political, economic, and social dynamics, it becomes evident that decisions made far from the region can directly affect its peoples and territories. At the same time, there is a need to support bottom-up approaches that respond to local priorities, bridge disciplinary divides, fully integrate the social sciences, and strengthen capacities within territories. Likewise, the training of new leaders should often encompass undervalued skills such as socio-emotional competencies (formerly referred to as “soft skills”), as well as art and multimedia, conflict management, the ability to work in uncertain contexts, and adaptive learning.

The workshop *Reshaping institutions for next generation conservation leaders in the Amazon* brought together a diverse group of educators, representatives of non-governmental organizations (NGOs), and emerging leaders from across Amazonian countries, creating a space for dialogue and rich exchange.

Over three full days, participants shared experiences, strategies, and lessons from their local contexts, alongside innovative educational initiatives that can be adapted and replicated in other regions. The meeting also strengthened cross-country collaboration, fostered a community of professionals committed to biocultural conservation, and explored practical tools to renew institutions and better support the next generation of leaders. As a result, participants identified and prioritized concrete steps to advance institutional transformation processes, while laying the groundwork for continued collaboration.

Held from July 29–31, 2025, in Santa Cruz de la Sierra, Bolivia, the event was organized by the Tropical Conservation and Development (TCD) Program at the University of Florida, in partnership with the Bolivian Institute of Forest Research (IBIF) and the Gordon and Betty Moore Foundation.

This event was the second in a series of five interconnected workshops designed to strengthen collaboration among educators, representatives of non-governmental organizations (NGOs), and young leaders from different Amazonian countries.

Workshop objectives

- To articulate a community working to promote new leaders in the Amazon.
- To share experiences of effective and innovative educational initiatives (community-based, Indigenous, professional development, primary/secondary education, and universities) that could be replicated in other Amazonian territories and localities.
- To strengthen connections among educators, civil society organizations, and young leaders from different Amazonian countries and contexts, fostering long-term collaborations.
- To exchange effective tools and approaches for transforming institutions and organizations to better empower the next generation of biocultural conservation leaders.

A workshop participant, representative of the Universidad Regional Amazónica Ikiam (IKIAM) in Ecuador, is presenting insights from her group's discussion.

Participant profile

The event was attended by 21 representatives from diverse organizations, including community-based organizations, youth groups, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), research and educational institutions (universities, primary schools, and technical institutes). Participants represented the United States and five Amazonian countries: Bolivia, Brazil, Colombia, Ecuador, and Peru. Fourteen participants were women and seven were men. The workshop actively integrated young leaders, bringing energy, hope, and intergenerational learning, as well as opportunities for mentoring and connection with a diversity of organizations and programs.

Workshop agenda

The workshop agenda was developed by the University of Florida team, thematic leaders, and a facilitator over approximately three months through weekly virtual meetings. The workshop was divided into three stages to achieve the objectives described above:

Day 1. Community building

Individual introductions and integration activities were conducted to create a safe and brave space where participants could freely express their opinions and ideas without fear. A harmonization ceremony facilitated by CNAMIB (National Confederation of Indigenous Women of Bolivia) stood out; this Amazonian ritual invokes harmony among participants so that ideas and the workshop itself can flow toward achieving the intended objectives. This activity, together with individual presentations involving life stories that motivated participants' leadership in conservation, generated shared emotions and fostered a comfortable environment in which ideas began to emerge. Despite representing different parts of the basin and diverse work and life contexts, participants began to come together around a common goal.

Day 2. Presentation of experiences and innovative approaches

Participants formed groups according to their areas of expertise, action, and interest around the following themes:

- Primary and secondary education.
- University education and technical careers.
- Alternative education.
- Strengthening key competencies and skills for conservation.

Challenges, consequences, and strategies to overcome those challenges were shared in each group. The facilitation team ensured that the youth were part of all groups and promoted their effective participation.

Day 3. Synthesis and next steps

Key lessons learned were identified, strategic pathways and alliances were discussed, and collective commitments were made to continue the work initiated during the workshop.

Initiatives that promote positive change

Throughout the workshop, participants illustrated ongoing initiatives, programs, and attributes that are reshaping institutions for the next generation of conservation leaders in Amazonia.

1. The influence of people who motivate youth engagement in conservation—such as family members, other young leaders, teachers, and trainers—was emphasized.
 - Young Indigenous Bolivians mentioned how IBIF (Bolivian Institute for Forest Research) trainers have been true mentors and sources of inspiration in their journeys.
 - An Indigenous woman shared how her grandparents' struggle to obtain land titles was a key motivation, and that her participation in the workshop was possible thanks to her husband's support in caring for their child during her absence.
2. Well-organized, strategic youth-focused activities gradually motivate active participation and youth-led action.
 - Some initiatives aim to strengthen cultural identity in the Amazon. For example, Tropenbos in Colombia offers courses for teachers to implement intercultural curricula with children and youth in their territories.
 - In Bolivia, the NGO ORE implements the School of Indigenous Governance and Territories and the Indigenous Journalism School, where youth take on leadership and technical roles in their territories.
3. Key competencies remain scarce in educational programs, particularly in communication and active listening, collaboration, leadership, conflict management, and project design.
 - Some institutions are implementing courses to develop these skills in the Amazon, such as IBIF, APCOB (Support for Indigenous and Peasant Communities of Eastern Bolivia), and CNAMIB (National Confederation of Indigenous Women of Bolivia).
 - Some graduate programs include these courses in their curricula, such as the Master's in Sustainability at Pontifical Catholic University of Ecuador and the Tropical Conservation and Development (TCD) Program at the University of Florida (USA), which trains several students from the Amazon.

4. Access to higher education for Amazonian youth remains a major challenge, though some innovative initiatives are working to close this gap.
 - In Brazil, public policy requires that 10% of admitted students and scholarships be reserved for minorities (Indigenous peoples, Afro-descendants, and the LGBTQI+ community).
 - Institutions such as the University of Pará and IPÊ's Higher Education School for Environmental Conservation and Sustainability (ESCAS) in Brazil, and PUCE (Pontifical Catholic University of Ecuador) in Ecuador, offer hybrid graduate programs focused on Amazonian issues.
5. Innovative educational approaches are also emerging that break with conventional educational paradigms.
 - In Ecuador and other countries, the Forest School initiative has been implemented; its goal is “learning through play, with the forest as the best classroom.”
 - Bolivian youth from PBACC (Bolivian Platform for Climate Action) use artistic resources for environmental education, including a well-known dinosaur costume to teach about extinction caused by climate change.

6. Greater access for young women to training and leadership spaces is possible due to changes in traditional gender roles and specific initiatives by various institutions.

- “A woman must choose between marriage and leadership,” noted an experienced Indigenous leader, reflecting traditional expectations of women’s domestic roles.
- A young Indigenous leader shared that she could only attend the workshop because her husband supported her and cared for their child during her absence. These examples reflect a generational shift in traditional gender roles within households.
- This shift has enabled greater access for young women to education and leadership opportunities, promoted by NGOs such as IBIF (Bolivian Institute for Forest Research) in Bolivia, which focus on capacity building for youth with a gender perspective in conservation.

7. Family and institutional support help reduce persistent gender gaps in access to education, especially in cases of adolescent pregnancy.

- Several cases were mentioned of young women who became mothers during adolescence and received support from family members—such as parents or grandparents—in the absence of or complementary to support from the child’s father.
- In Bolivia, CNAMIB (National Confederation of Indigenous Women of Bolivia) offers courses and support for the empowerment of Indigenous women.

- IKIAM University in Ecuador provides scholarships and specific financial assistance for adolescent mothers.
- In Bolivia, IBIF contracts childcare services and facilitates transportation from communities so that participants in workshops and training activities can remain close to their children. Meeting schedules are also adjusted to participants’ availability.
- Nevertheless, there remains a critical need across all educational levels for childcare spaces that enable women’s access to employment and education.

8. The necessary attributes of education in the Amazon to train future conservation leaders should primarily be transformative, inclusive, contextualized, intercultural, intergenerational, transversal, and value-based.

Collective Insights for Moving Forward

Participants emphasized the transformative role of specific actions—such as radio programs and seed funds for sustainable socio-productive initiatives led by youth—in enhancing youth participation, along with the influence of mentors, women leaders, and lived struggles such as conflicts over territorial rights. Voices of Indigenous youth highlighted the importance of cultural identity, ancestral knowledge, stories of their ancestors' struggles, and the challenges of their territories in shaping a sense of belonging and motivation to remain and contribute to their communities.

However, critical gaps persist in communication, collaboration, conflict management, and project design skills, compounded by limited access to higher education. Due to economic constraints and lack of support, the line between continuing education and abandoning aspirations for advancement can be very thin, making training processes even more crucial.

Gender dynamics also emerged, including “new masculinities” that enable women’s leadership despite persistent cultural barriers.

Finally, participants envisioned an education for Amazonian conservation leaders that is human-centered, inclusive, intercultural, intergenerational, collaborative, and transformative. These attributes should be present in every level of education (primary, secondary, higher) and in programs that strengthen the competencies and skills of youth and women.

1. Amazonian leadership pathways

- Amazonian leadership is forged at the intersection of personal passion, community experiences, and training opportunities.
- Youth, educators, and organizational representatives highlighted the influence of family members, mentors, and support networks, as well as strategies such as communication, environmental education, and participatory research.
- These pathways reflect resilient leadership, rooted in cultural identity and committed to protecting Amazonian territories.

2. Causes, challenges, consequences, and effective actions in every level of education and in programs that strengthen youth and women in conservation.

	Primary and secondary education	Alternative education (to standard schooling)	University education and technical careers	Strengthening competencies and skills of youth and women
Causes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Colonization and imposed education models; · Lack of recognition of Indigenous knowledge; · Policies without effective implementation; · Precarious teacher training, deficient infrastructure; · Digital divide in rural communities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Legacy of colonization and discrimination; · Lack of supportive public policies; devaluation of local, ancestral, and Indigenous knowledge; · Alternative education certificates with limited recognition in the formal labor market. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Environmental degradation that reduces local opportunities; · Structural poverty; · Geographic dispersion and isolation of communities that limit student access and retention; · Centralized and rigid policies that do not respond to territorial realities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Low youth participation; · Limited access to technology; · Lack of knowledge of digital tools.
Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Building education that is relevant to the territory and dialogues with local languages; · Knowledge, and practices; overcoming rigid curricula and multigrade conditions without specialization; · Expanding equitable access to external programs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Building an education system that recognizes and articulates community knowledge with competencies for personal and professional development, ensuring intergenerationality, interculturality, inclusion, and equity. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Designing inclusive admission mechanisms; · Curricula disconnected from local knowledge; · Misalignment between institutional demands, teaching capacities, and student needs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Closing digital, gender, and intergenerational gaps; · Strengthening leadership and autonomy for conservation.
Consequences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · School dropout, forced migration; · Loss of cultural identity, weakening of local knowledge transmission; · Disadvantages in access to urban education. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Loss of ancestral knowledge on sustainable territorial management; · Isolation and lack of identity among youth; · Limited economic opportunities and weakened community resilience. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Exclusion of Indigenous and rural students; loss of individual talent; · Exclusionary and homogeneous university models; · Weak integration of interculturality, even in Indigenous universities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Loss of traditional knowledge; · Limited youth participation; barriers to women's leadership, affecting project sustainability and community participation in conservation initiatives.
Strategies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Formal recognition of Indigenous knowledge; · Strengthening intercultural education; · Contextualized teacher training; · Development of adapted curricula; · Creation of innovation networks and continuous support. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Contextualization and territorialization of learning; · Holistic methodologies with a humanizing approach; · Community strengthening and cultural identity; · Narratives that make local knowledge visible; · Integration of art, multimedia, and outdoor education. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Scholarships, financial support, and comprehensive accompaniment; · Inclusive quotas and flexibility in certification; · Relevant curricula linked to the Amazonian context; · Promotion of interculturality and academic diversity; · Adapted hybrid and virtual programs; · Strengthening faculty through certifications and active methodologies; · Creation of universities or programs with interdisciplinary and innovative approaches. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Continuous, territory-based training; · Development of socio-emotional skills; · Appropriation of technologies, economic alternatives for independence; · Innovative communication methodologies (art, multimedia) that promote the protagonism of youth and women in conservation.

3. Innovative approaches and educational methods for Amazonian Education

These approaches are implemented through the organizations and institutions represented by workshop participants.

3.1. Art and multimedia

- Art and multimedia are used to preserve traditional knowledge, Indigenous languages, and cultural heritage, integrating knowledge from elders and youth.
 - Youth actively participate in creating videos, short films, music, dance, drawing, and photography, developing technical and narrative skills.
 - These strategies strengthen leadership, autonomy, and citizenship, promoting youth participation and visibility of local realities.
 - Intergenerational transmission of knowledge, reflection on territory, and communication of socio-environmental issues are fostered.
 - Public and scientific advocacy is promoted through dissemination in digital media and social networks, contributing to cultural and environmental sustainability and conservation.
- University students are connected with real-world problems and local actors, fostering leadership and participation.
 - Expanded remote access allows diversification of student profiles, including youth, professionals, farmers, park rangers, and community leaders.

3.2. Amazonian sociodramas: Education, Leadership, and Conservation

- Through sociodramas, participants explored challenges and strategies related to education and leadership in the Amazon.
- Topics included educational inclusion, youth motherhood, intercultural accompaniment, and student retention.
- Socio-environmental conflicts and the need for collaboration among public and private actors to achieve effective biocultural conservation were represented.
- Transmission of ancestral knowledge and intergenerational participation were highlighted as tools for leadership and territorial defense.
- Women's empowerment was emphasized, integrating young people and mothers into forest governance and protection.
- The activity fostered creativity, reflection, and dialogue, combining performing arts, music, costumes, and visual storytelling.

3.3. Virtual education

- Hybrid and intercultural programs are used, combining in-person and virtual classes adapted to local contexts.
- Digital and technical skills for environmental monitoring and socio-environmental conflict resolution are taught.

3.4. Interdisciplinary and intercultural approaches

- Recovery and transmission of traditional knowledge—history, Indigenous languages, plant use, weaving, and ceramics—are promoted, strengthening cultural identity.
- Local knowledge, natural resources, and culture are integrated into educational programs through creative laboratories, art, and innovative methodologies.
- Students and leaders are trained in project management and interdisciplinary approaches.
- Practical and collaborative learning is encouraged, including territorial monitoring, environmental control, and technology use.

3.5. Comprehensive support and socio-emotional skills

- Skills such as organization, responsibility, cooperation, and teamwork are developed through practical activities and educational projects.
- Leadership, youth empowerment, cultural resilience, communication, and conflict resolution are fostered.

- Some universities offer tutoring, personalized support, and financial and psychological assistance to facilitate educational transitions and address academic and personal challenges.
- Collaboration networks, mentorships, and socio-emotional skills are strengthened, promoting well-being, balance, and rights advocacy among students from rural and Indigenous contexts.

3.6. Gender equity

- Leadership and governance programs with intercultural approaches and women's participation are developed, integrating practical and theoretical learning.
- Training adapted to the realities of Indigenous women is offered, incorporating traditional knowledge, gender perspectives, and non-conventional methodologies.
- Community promoters are trained to prevent and address gender-based violence, fostering leadership, empowerment, and active participation of women in their territories.

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About the project ‘Power of Connections’

The “Power of Connections” project is led by the Tropical Conservation and Development (TCD) Program at the University of Florida’s Center for Latin American Studies, in partnership with the Gordon and Betty Moore Foundation. “Learning lessons and strengthening coalitions for Amazon conservation” is at the heart of this project, which seeks to connect people and collaboratively develop pathways for the sustainable conservation of the Pan-Amazon region. This project is funded by the Gordon and Betty Moore Foundation through grant GBMF13270.

About TCD

The mission of the Tropical Conservation and Development (TCD) Program is to connect theory and practice to promote biodiversity conservation, sustainable resource use, and human well-being in the tropics and beyond. TCD is a research and training program of the Center for Latin American Studies, with 10 core faculty and approximately 100 affiliate faculty across the University of Florida campus. TCD has a long history of collaborating with partner organizations in the Amazon and supporting networks of conservation professionals dedicated to sustainable development.

About the Moore Foundation

The Gordon and Betty Moore Foundation promotes scientific discovery, environmental conservation, and the unique character of the San Francisco Bay Area. Since 2001, the Moore Foundation’s Andes-Amazon Initiative has helped conserve more than 400 million hectares of the Amazon. By 2031, the initiative aims to bring 70 percent of the Amazon biome (forest cover) and the freshwater ecosystems that support it under effective management and conservation. Visit Moore.org and follow @MooreFound to learn more.

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